

A Study on the Preference of Digital Advertising to Traditional Advertising in the Developing World

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Abstract

In an ever-changing world, adaptability is a key feature; It is necessary for a business. Technology is constantly growing, and businesses need to continually upgrade their marketing strategy as well as their plans to keep advancing on targeted goals. After the launch of the Internet, there was a substantial change in marketing. Businesses are no longer just using a traditional way to advertise their products or services and are shifting towards a more modern way called digital marketing. ("How has digital marketing changed traditional marketing?") ("How has digital marketing changed traditional marketing?") The broad scope of the internet is a fantastic opportunity for massive growth, especially for businesses that are raising their digital marketing budgets. "Marketing is a concept that has always evolved over the years." ("How has digital marketing changed traditional marketing?") ("How has digital marketing changed traditional marketing?") Billboards, brochures, radio, television, etc. Traditional marketing using legacy mediums is shifting towards digital marketing that focuses on digital platforms with advertisements. The world is going digital, and today's marketing requires a more modern and technological approach, but various traditional marketing strategies are still used today. A strong business is one that can adapt to any situation and is ready to face challenges. The key to an effective marketing strategy is an adaptive feature that can constantly change based on relevant and correct data. To reach targeted customers in the most effective ways, your marketing strategy should not depend solely on a precise type of marketing, as both traditional and digital marketing can work together and reinforce the brand message you portray. The focus should be on how to blend different marketing approaches and achieve maximum results effectively. This article examines how advertising and demand based on digital technology overturns the traditional and is the reason for preference.

Keywords: *Digital Advertising in the Developing World, Digital Advertising, Technology and Advertising, Traditional Advertising, Advertising, Advertising*

1. Introduction

Traditional vs. Digital

Distinctive Features Rapidly growing technology requires a more digital solution and replaces some parts of the traditional marketing approach that has been used for years. While traditional marketing strategies focus on selling products, modern marketing focuses more on discovering the customer's needs and increasing customer satisfaction through modern methods such as social media marketing. This modern method focuses on how to communicate with the audience, understand their needs, and then give them maximum satisfaction so they come back to make that purchase. Digital Marketing makes it easier for businesses, especially small businesses, to grow, whereas with traditional marketing previously this was a minor possibility. Since the world of digital marketing is so vast and the trend is always changing, it is important for digital marketers to stay up to date and understand what is going on.

Brands, social media marketing, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), email marketing, mobile marketing (SMS, MMS in-app marketing), content marketing, etc. can use various tools for digital marketing such as Changing a business's website is a crucial step. Start your digital marketing campaign and a business should make sure it reaches potential customers and creates the best customer experiences.

Today, businesses can use print ads, direct mail, TV ads, etc. He does not need to do a lot of work on it and wait for his messages to grasp his target audience. Digital marketing is an effective approach to reach a wider audience as well as reach the target audience with exactly accurate and specific demographic information. With this advantage, traditional marketing has become older, plus customers find it easier to skip an ad in which they are no longer interested. The enormous

growth of digital marketing does not mean that businesses should completely neglect traditional marketing strategy. It is true that digital marketing has been a subject of hype and is still growing today, but traditional marketing strategies can reinforce your message and complement your marketing strategies. Therefore, it is important for marketers to know that these two approaches together can be used to support each other. It is especially important to know the difference as well as the advantages and disadvantages of these two strategies, so do not exclude them from each other. Following industry trends

2. Planning an Effective Strategy

Planning an effective strategy requires setting a large budget for the digital marketing campaign, including a wide variety of platforms that can allow the use of the data collected. (“How has digital marketing changed traditional marketing?”) Companies are looking for a marketing team that is not only creative but knowledgeable about revenue-raising activities . Businesses need a strong focus on better customer experience. Digital Marketers must craft an efficient strategy to win the competition between competitors and the industry. Companies also need digital marketing professionals who can analyze and improve user experience and behavior so they can lead the company in increasing profits in the global world. When you are trying to scale up your business, it means you are up for a bigger challenge and need to find the best strategy or tactics to follow industry trends . With the changing age, people who buy and sell goods and services over the internet and the use of internet technology are always increasing. To succeed more effectively than the competition, their customers need to have a full awareness of what they are, how they can be met and what new demands they can generate (Raluca, 2016).

appears to differ significantly from traditional marketing in that it focuses on the fourth promotion . On the other hand, Digital marketing is extremely effective as it includes all four Ps of marketing. Instead, it uses each separately, often much better than traditional marketing (LYFE Marketing, 2021); (Jamil et al., 2021).

The theory and technique of advertising and promotion in new directions, often by distribution platforms, to reach customers and users in a fast, convenient, customized and spend approach called digital promotion (Todor, 2016). (“TRANSITION FROM TRADITIONAL MARKETING TO DIGITAL MARKETING: A ...”)

The targeted, quantitative yet collaborative promotion of items and/or services uses electronic techniques to reach, persuade and engage customers, often referred to as digital marketing. (“Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...”) The main purpose is to use various digital marketing strategies to promote businesses, create preferences and increase purchases (Raluca, 2016).

According to forecasts, by 2026, the digital market will grow from \$38.5 billion in 2017 to \$200 billion. The main purpose is to promote companies, create preferences and increase sales by using various digital marketing tactics (Raluca, 2016). According to estimates, the online market is growing between \$20 trillion in 2018 and \$1 trillion in 2026. Increasing internet technology, smartphone adoption, and the rollout of 4G and 5G networks are key drivers of e-commerce change (<http://www.ibef.org>).

literature on change from traditional marketing , this study will be an attempt to answer these broad questions.

- *What is the status of academic studies on the transition from traditional to digital marketing?*
- *How has scientific research influenced both transitions? (Pilsto et al., 2008).*

Cho & Kang (2006) found that internet research has grown significantly over the past decade with the contribution of a wide range of followers and theoretical and methodological perspectives. Many of the cited publications and articles, together with their common citation behavior, are used to create a holistic "picture" of the region and highlight key influencers and contributors. Bibliometric analysis provides prospects for establishing a “baseline” for the growing field of

internet advertising and allows future scholars to understand where the discipline came from and to track its evolution over time (Pilato et al., 2008).

3. Literature review

The main assumptions of the study are that the frequency with which a series of articles or patents are cited is a measure of the impact of a series of articles. (Pilato et al.; 2008) evaluates the most cited authors, publications, and the overall structure of the disciplines, shows how scientific research has impacted the fields of Online Marketing, and answers broad topics using a joint review. It was observed to be quite skewed compared to the patent bibliometric, with few high impact and minimal impact on many patents and articles. The study (Chaffey & Palron; 2012) examined how companies can use web techniques to understand digital distribution methods to implement techniques to set up digital advertising improvement initiatives, as well as how individuals, strategy, evaluation, and technology can be combined.

According to research (Gupta et al; 2020), which used the Scopus database to provide a quantitative and qualitative assessment of e-commerce research in India in a global context, India is considered the sixth most productive country in terms of study profiles . (“Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...”) It provides a brief bibliometric analysis of the top fifteen global organizations, the top fifteen global authors, the most important subject areas and the best channels for research communications, and the most cited articles.

(Zhou et al; 2020) evaluated the bibliometric analysis used to identify the characteristics and evolution of social commerce research from 2003 to 2018 using the Web of Science database. The study found that there is a lot of collaborative research in the social commerce field in the form of multi-author publications, and the main research topics can be differentiated according to the LLR ratio:

- *The evolution of social commerce.*

- *Relationship between customer and seller*
- *Consumer trust is important in the context of social buying.*

The results of the study revealed the current understanding based on trade and system development views. The study's findings include seven perspectives on the digitization of entrepreneurship, covering topics such as the digital economy, fundraising, and the collaborative economy (Kraus et al; 2019; Veklenko; 2020), demonstrating a succinct understanding of the factors that drive final purchase intention along with purchase intention.

literature on the effectiveness of online advertising and to reveal the main factors. The study's findings suggested that the online advertising space has been heavily influenced by technological advances and is increasingly focused on interdisciplinarity, providing online marketers with new insights into the effectiveness of online advertising and the key determinants of effectiveness prediction models.

Chung et al, 2020, the development of the innovation management study was explored using a co-citation approach with visual mapping that included citation analysis and identification of key citations, contributors, and top publications. In digital innovation research, the main research flow is done as in cluster analysis. Based on common citations, the study discovered four thematic clusters and seven thematic clusters based on bibliometric analysis. The study aims to map the state of digital market studies using bibliometric and analyzed research data methods such as Scopus and Vos Viewer, and the findings show which country, research institutions and individual researchers are more productive in digital studies (Nangoy et al., 2020).). (“Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...”)

(Kraus et al., 2019), the special issue in the results of the study, Virtual Innovations and Experiments, included seven articles on the digitalization of innovation, covering key topics such as fintech, fundraising, and the collaborative economy. (Liu et al., 2017) searched publishers and discovered the highest rise of online innovation process using graphical mappings and a co-citation methodology and evaluated by bibliometric analysis and key references. "The main research

stream in digital innovation research and cluster analysis is also conducted." ("TRANSITION FROM TRADITIONAL MARKETING TO DIGITAL MARKETING: A ...") (Verma 2021), it was stated that the citation trend, context, keyword, and co-citation analysis related to digital marketing published in the last few years from the Scopus database were targeted with 296 publications where 286 publications were evaluated for study. Vos Viewer and Voyant tool are used to analyze the data . The result of the study showed the most research on digital marketing in 2019, while the most citations were observed in 2017 and the most citations per publication were observed in 2010-2013.

4. Bibliometric Study

The bibliometric study is used to evaluate 12 years of articles published in journals related to basic DMC. The study provided academics with thematic insights and conclusions that are truly forward-thinking ways to develop successful DMC. (Almahri et al., 2021) has reviewed the latest academic research trends on e-commerce themes in China and has provided engaging guides to government, IT policy makers, and academic researchers. ("Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...") The study identified the need to focus on such issues and themes, were China lags other countries in e-commerce. In the early spring of 2016, Microsoft introduced the concept of speech as a platform where artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language interaction enabled new ways to communicate with interactive technology (Folstad & Brandtzaeg , 2017).

Many commercial and private domains have been conquered by domain-specific assistance in the form of chatbots (de Reuver et al., 2020). Facebook introduced tools for designing chatbots for Messenger, which is also its messaging program (Folstad & Brandtzaeg , 2017). There's also Google Search, a built-in robot in the Allo chat app, and system updates to the Android platform, which excels in all of them, but is clumsy. The transition between providing a massive speaking style for robots and providing interface dynamics is represented by development for robots.

Developers gain real freedom regarding characteristics and interaction approaches are defined in contemporary generation graphical interfaces that provide full representation of dynamic network components. The word “ chatbot ” consists of the term’s “ chat ” and “robot.” Originally, the word " chatbot " was related to software applications that imitated human speech using a content communication network. Chatbots have a text or input layer that offers customers the flexibility to connect with instantly powered technology (Wang & Petrina , 2013).

Chatbots, also known as multilingual bots, are now built for a range of uses. Artificial intelligence (AI) and text analytics (NLP) advances are changing the way virtual assistants collaborate with humans (Ngugen & Sidorova , 2018; Jain et al., 2018). As content and monologue interaction advances, robots have become more accessible and common (Bittner et al., 2019). Siri, Google Now , Cortane , Facebook M, Blackberry Assistant , Braina , Tenco , Speaktoit Some of the new smart assistants such as Assistant , Hound , Amazon Echo (Alexa) were created with the aim of assisting people by voice in their daily lives. Chatbot has grown exponentially because of the emergence of these services (Janssen et al., 2017).

The ability of robots and interface design to use natural language to facilitate speaking activities while delivering usable outputs is a critical success factor. (“Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...”) Google Assistant is a dialog, and innovative, with its capacity to stream a conversation through multiple phrases. Chatbots can have a wide variety of features that require the use of terms such as multilingual agents, chatbots, and virtual assistants. In this analysis, the word “ chatbot ” refers to an autonomous speaking entity that deals with purpose- or task-oriented discourse through a text-based medium (Chaves and Gerosa , 2020).

As a result of robotics, work is characterized by the interaction of humans and robots (Lehrer et al., 2018; Schneider et al., 2018). Simultaneously, linguistic bots can be developed to influence perceptions (Fogg , 2002; Mirsch et al., 2017; Oinas-Kukkonen & Harjumaa , 2009; Weinmann et al., 2016). (“Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...”) In this extreme

perspective, people are considered "artworks molded and used by technologies (system) rather than vice versa" (Demetis & Lee, 2018).

As a result,

- (1) *Participation,*
- (2) *Cognition and*
- (3) *individual action is important.*

A chatbot is a piece of software that communicates with people using natural language processing and predictive analysis to understand queries and respond appropriately (Mittal et al., 2016). Chatbots have become increasingly popular in real-world applications due to their ability to precisely mimic human representatives during conversations. Chatbots are available 24 hours a day, seven days a week, and cost less than humans (Mittal et al., 2016). (“Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...”)

5. The Role of Virtual Assistants in Advertising

These days, many technology companies have introduced devices that support voice assistant technology to consumers. According to a recent study by global audit firm PWC, 1,000 consumers aged 18 to 64 were surveyed to raise awareness about virtual assistant technology. Now a day, virtual assistants and voice-controlled devices are used by 100,000 people in their routine lives. Artificial smart assistants most used by consumers such as Amazon's Alexa and Google Assistant (K.Jones , 2018). In the words of Matt Thompson, Bitty 's chief product officer, "voice assistant is the new operating system" used by users to access data, added information and entertainment. Virtual Personal Assistants (VPAs) are software programs that allow businesses to naturally interact with customers, sort their questions, and respond to their needs. Consumers can give two types of input to the virtual personal assistant, such as Text and voice interfaces.

Recently, with the developments in information technology and broadband internet, the service has become widespread and the speed of access to shopping sites is increasing. Due to these changes, companies inevitably entered the digital environment. Therefore, as the communication rules change, the field and definition of marketing also changes. With the development of information technologies, traditional marketing methods are leaving their place to digital day by day. Companies that follow technology can easily communicate with their customers interactively while offering products or services. As in traditional marketing, it is especially important to communicate well with customers and to determine their needs and wishes in digital marketing. While companies using digital marketing are effective with bilateral communication, those who are not included in this race are gradually getting away from the competition. The biggest advantage of digital marketing is to reach the target audience correctly using social media and search engines. This study tries to explain the digital marketing periods and advantages, the transition and difference between traditional and digital marketing. (“Travel from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing - ResearchGate”)

6. Firms Follow Various Strategies to Adapt to Competition and Are Effective

In the last century, companies have made heroic efforts to leave their competitors behind in the process of globalization and branding. Firms follow various strategies to adapt to competition and are effective. In addition, with the increase in customer demands, meeting and satisfying customer needs has become much more difficult. Also, since the beginning of the 21st century, technology has been advancing drastically, causing changes in every aspect of our lives. Firms were unavoidably affected by these changes and started to use information and communication technologies more in the market. One of the advantages of the Internet is that everyday problems can be solved easily and quickly. In addition, consumer consciousness is taking a different shape with developments in technology. Consumers can now find and compare various products and services, especially with the help of social media. Also, companies can author α :Assist.

It has become especially important to know the type of search engines consumers use and whether they can find specific companies on their search engine maps. (“Travel from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing”) Advertisements on the Internet have replaced the advertisements that were once famous in newspapers. In this study, you will be given conceptual information about the initial stages of digital marketing. Then, digital marketing ads and traditional ads will be compared in terms of measurability. Finally, the advantages of interactive media will be evaluated. (“Travel from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing”)

II. Traditional Marketing As a result of the two world wars, countries have struggled to revive their economies. However, in this transition period, product and service demands cannot meet the needs of consumers. Because production was limited, companies could sell every piece of their product. A few years later, the welfare level rose, and the economy became unstable. Then, with the introduction of television into western societies, the world gained a brand-new perspective on everything. As the balance of power shifted from suppliers to consumers due to changes in market share, suppliers began to use various promises to attract and persuade customers. This situation has caused customers to question a product or service before purchasing it (Karahasan, 2013:15). popularity of the concepts of "brand" and "advertisement" while introducing new concepts . (“Travel from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing”) And that was when the concept of marketing was introduced. Mass production products became widespread. With this innovative marketing approach, companies had to change their perspectives and put consumers at the center to meet their needs at the maximum level. Firms that adopt the traditional marketing approach have given importance to the customers rather than their own structures and have tried to meet the needs of the customers (İslamoğlu, 2013:18).

The value of the marketing program for customers can be seen in the positive difference between the benefit customers receive when consuming products and the purpose of traditional marketing is to provide time, place, and ownership benefits. Therefore, the essence of marketing is to create

value for customers and motivate them to buy. In other words, the goal is to change the perception of customers.

7. Digital Marketing Companies and the Opportunities of Advances in Technology

Since the beginning of the 21st century, Digital Marketing Companies have undergone many changes in a noticeably brief time thanks to the opportunities provided by the advances in technology. The use of information and communication technologies is increasing day by day by companies to promote their products and get to know their customers. This increase has been linear over the years (Tan et al., 2004:83).

Also, companies use IT to trade with other companies. “Business to Electronic infrastructure is used in this system called " business " (B2B) (İnan, 2002:124). Firms actively use electronic commerce and digital marketing to surpass their competitors (Bulut et al. 2006).

In this way, a two-way connection is established between customers and companies. Digital marketing is quite different from traditional marketing (Varnalı, 2012:39). Since the conditions of digital marketing are different, brands that cannot be competitors under normal conditions can compete. Digital marketing aims to serve customers as quickly as possible and seeks guidance from customers rather than trying to change their perceptions like traditional marketing. (“Travel from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing”) Thanks to digital marketing, customers can access products and services easily and quickly, compare related products and have an idea about them, thus speeding up the purchasing process. In addition, while the time spent in shopping is normally seen as a big problem, this problem seems to have disappeared with online shopping (Cop & Oyan, 2010:100).

The main purpose of online marketing is to use existing infrastructure to make a profit. The development, pricing, promotion, and distribution of goods is also done online. The benefits of digital marketing can be considered as a revolution for the marketing world (Karaca, 2012:40).

8. Stages of Digital Marketing

- a) Customer Acquisition The first thing to do at this stage is to attract customers and followers to the website. There are many techniques for gaining customers (Hoffman and Novak, 2000). Some of the most used techniques are search engine optimizations , search engine ads, email marketing, social network marketing, mobile marketing, viral marketing, and affiliate marketing. The purpose of Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is to bring together the target audience and the web page through search engines. In other words, it is about being at the top of the search results list. A large part of the search engine revenue in the online advertising industry is covered by SEO. Investments in optimization provide companies with rapid profitability. In short, SEO helps to list search engine results and get them at the top of the list (Xing and Ain , 2006:3).
- b) In a type of search engine advertising system known as Pay Per Click (PPC), users pay a set fee to search engines. (“Travel from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing - Global Journals”) The logic is to pay per click. Web pages only pay when their ads are clicked, and users are directed to their page. Search engine marketing (SEM) uses PPC (Chen et al., 2011:4545). E-mail marketing is a type of marketing in which customers are reached via e-mail to provide information about certain products and services (Korkmaz, 2002:38). (“(PDF) Travel from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing - ResearchGate”) It is important in this type of marketing (Chittenden and Rattie , 2003:203).
- c) Social network marketing is the process of attracting customers to relevant websites using social media elements. The main purpose of this type of marketing is to advertise brands, products, and services by taking the opinions and suggestions of customers (De Vries et al. 2012:84). (“Travel from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing”) Recently, social networks are frequently used as a marketing channel. Marketers are also interested in these

networks that contain personal information about users. Revenue partnership is based on companies paying per product or service they sell online (Duffy , 2005:162).

d) Viral marketing, on the other hand, is the voluntary sharing of information or ideas about products or services with friends via e-mail (Richardson and Domingos , 2002:2). Viral marketing also saves time by influencing customers' purchasing decisions. Viral marketing is increasing, especially in periods when visuality is at the forefront (Argen and Tokay, 2006:232-233). The six factors of viral marketing are listed below (Wilson, 2000:1-2):

- i. Free service Easy advertising
- ii. Established network
- iii. Fast transfer
- iv. Interesting growth
- v. Other infrastructures
- vi. The concept of “mobile” has also undergone some changes with technological developments.

An example of a low engagement strategy is for customers to use links placed at the bottom of articles to share them. High engagement strategy includes a more initiative-taking approach by using social networks such as Twitter's Facebook (Ünal, 2011:75-76).

Also known as Word-of-Mouth Marketing, viral marketing is based on sharing ideas about certain products. The starting point is a widely disseminated online message. Also, this marketing technique costs extraordinarily little if any. In addition, the fact that customers consult with people they trust about products also speeds up the purchasing process.

9. Digital Marketing and Measurability

Digital ads have different parameters compared to traditional marketing. Traditional ads are measured using methods such as Gross Rating Score (GRP). More specific methods such as CPM (Cost Per Mile) and CPC (Cost Per Click) are used for advertisements in digital media (Açıklal

and Çelikol , 2012:13). For advertising companies, the internet comes with realistic values , followed by measurability. Advertising is gaining increased importance every day as it is used to reach customers by providing information about products. Advertising helps to create a positive perception about the products and therefore gains the loyalty and loyalty of the customers. Customers, on the other hand, can make healthy decisions thanks to the detailed information about the products and services in the advertisements (Gökaliiler and Sabuncuğlu , 2008:1314-17). Digital media. Moreover, advertising in digital channels is much more efficient than traditional advertisements. This leads to high-speed growth of the digital marketing industry. Depending on the developments in technology, we can encounter new advertising methods every day. The increase in band capacity and the easy accessibility of technology today makes it easier to reach the target audience with the help of video ads. VII. Advantages of Digital Media The biggest advantage of digital marketing is to reach the target audience by using interactive media. (“Travel from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing”) Certain models have been developed to get the most efficient results from digital marketing. The moment when customer needs and requests are met correctly is also the moment when customer satisfaction and loyalty are provided (Molla and Licker , 2001:136).

addition, studies show that companies that use online marketing effectively attach immense importance to mutual communication to increase customer loyalty and loyalty (Srinivasan et al. 2002). In addition to all these, digital media provides competitive advantage, reduces personnel employment and advertising costs. Thanks to the internet, customers today have all the information they need about products or services at their feet. In this way, they can easily compare products and services, and in this way, they can quickly decide which ads to buy.

Search engines like Google, Yahoo, Bing and Ask are available 24/7. The number of online shopping sites has increased considerably. In addition, basic problems such as distribution, storage, payment, and security have been overcome. Distribution systems have been developed with infrastructure investments. Shipping and cargo operations are now conducted smoothly. Banks, financial institutions, and retailers jointly develop return policies along with countermeasures

against payment fraud. Most companies make large investments to create the infrastructure of safe shopping (Karahasan, 2013:62-65).

Google Analytics , marketers can remarket to consumers they know are interacting with their website's content in a particular way. The combination of this historical data with purposeful artificial intelligence developed by Google creates a chance to communicate with future components. This is an opportunity that cannot be provided because traditional marketing methods lack the power.

10. Conclusion

Information from viewers is also included in historical statistics. Audience information is statistics that include search keywords that lead people to a particular website, time spent on site, precision of pages viewed, devices used, and much more. This data can help companies discover and precisely target new audiences they may not have known before. A company may have a keen sense of who constitutes its target market and what type of marketing is most successful for that demographic but using Google Analytics can help ensure that prospects are not lost. This is especially true when efforts made using traditional marketing are paired with those made using digital marketing. Because the cost of traditional advertising can be quite expensive, it is essential to leverage the data and insights gained through digital marketing to make the dollar spent on other types of advertising more successful to offset the prohibitive cost of traditional advertising. For example, if an organization's use of Google Analytics reveals that most site visitors and users who respond to calls to action are concentrated in a small number of specific geographic locations, that organization may decide to restrict distribution. Instead of distributing brochures citywide, simply convert them to a few specific zip codes. Because those who receive the brochures are more likely to support the organization than people who live elsewhere, doing so helps the organization save money and increase its return on investment. Never in the history of the philanthropy industry has it been more important to reach untouched audiences and highlight businesses in creative ways.

Nonprofits can keep up with the rapidly changing environment if they adopt a flexible and adaptable marketing approach. An adaptive strategy is one that focuses primarily on digital advertising, but also includes certain traditional ad formats. This type of strategy can help nonprofits increase their returns and build a stronger brand image among their communities and supporters. Using digital advertising solutions such as Google Analytics and useful tracking and reporting tools can help charities gather valuable information that can be used to fine-tune other advertising initiatives that are already being implemented for the greatest possible impact.

11. References

- A Munshi, MSS MUNSHI (2012), "Digital marketing: A new buzz word", International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research, Vol.2 Issue 7.
- Abbruzzese , J., Ingram, D., & Click, S. (2020). The coronavirus pandemic drove life online. "It may never return: What passes for normal life now happens almost entirely online." ("The coronavirus pandemic drove life online. It may never return. - NBC News") ("Impact of Covid 19 Pandemic on Digital Marketing – A Review - SlideShare") NBC News, 28th March.
- Alshaketheep , K., Salah, A., Alomari , K., Khaled, A., & Abu Jay , A. (2020). Digital Marketing during COVID 19: Consumer's Perspective. WSEAS TRANSACTIONS ON BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS, 17, 831-841. doi: 10.37394/23207.2020.17.81
- Argan, Text and Mehpare Tokay Argan (2006), "Viral Marketing or on the Internet Oral to mouth Advertisement : A Theoretical Framework ", Anadolu University Social Journal of Sciences , Issue: two, pp. 231-250.5.
- Bala , M., & Verma, D. (2018). A critical review of digital marketing. M. Bala , D. Verma (2018). A Critical Review

- of Digital Marketing. (“A Critical Review of Digital Marketing - SSRN”) (“A Critical Review of Digital Marketing - SSRN”) International Journal of Management, IT & Engineering, 8(10), 321-339.
- Bauer HH, T. Reichardt, SJ Barnes, and M.M. Neumann, (2005), “Driving Consumer Acceptance of Mobile Marketing: A Theoretical Framework and Empirical Study”, Journal of Electronic Commerce Research, vol.6 (3), pp. 181–192.6.
- Bhayani, S. and Vachhani, N., 2014. Internet marketing vs Traditional Marketing Comparative Analysis. FIIB Business Review, 3(3), pp.53-63.
- Bulut, ZA, Öngören, B., and Engin, K. (2006). in SMEs electronic of trade usage : Istanbul example . Birth University Journal, 7(2), 150-161.7.
- Chen, C. Y., Shih, BY, Chen, ZS, and Chen, TH (2011). The exploration of internet marketing strategy by search engine optimization: a critical review and comparison . African Journal of Business Management, 5(12), 4644-4649.
- Crushing It. Retrieved 22 October 2021, from <https://www.martechadvisor.com/articles/digitaltransformation/traditional-to-digital-marketing-lessons-to-learn-from-legacybrands>
- Efendioglu, YD (2016). Travel from traditional marketing to digital marketing. Global Journal of Management and Business Research: E, 8.
- Enterprise, D., Transformation, D., & Grover, V. (2021). Transitioning from Traditional to Digital: 5 Legacy Brands
- Fogg, BJ (2002). "Persuasive technology: using computers to change what we think and do." (“Persuasive Technology: Using Computers to Change What We Think and Do ...”) (“Persuasive technology: using computers to change what we ... - Ubiquity”) Ubiquity, 2002(December), 2.

- Følstad , A., & Brandtzæg , PB (2017). Chatbots and the new world of HCI interactions, 24(4), 38-42.
- Gupta, K., Hajika , R., Pai, YS, Duenser , A., Lochner, M., & Billinghamurst , M. (2020, March). ("Advanced Methods for User Evaluation in Enterprise AR") "Measuring human trust in a virtual assistant using physiological sensing in virtual reality." ("Measuring Human Trust in a Virtual Assistant using Physiological ...") ("Pai Yun Suen - Empathic Computing Lab") "In 2020 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR) (pp. 756-765)." ("Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...") ("Transition from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing: A ...") IEEE.
- Gupta, S., 2020. Digital marketing. 2nd ed. McGraw Hill, pp.3-4.
- Jain, N., Ahuja, V., & Medury , Y. (2018). Digital marketing optimization. In Digital Marketing and Consumer Engagement: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications (pp. 559-567). ("Faculty Research | SCMS Pune") ("Faculty Research | SCMS Pune") IGI Global.
- Jamil, JM, Rusle , R., Zolkipli , MF, & Shaharane , INM (2021). Perceived Usefulness of Instagram as a Marketing Tool in Higher Education Institutions. Journal of ICT in Education, 8(1), 104-113.
- Janssen, A., Passlick , J., Cardona, DR, & Breitner , MH (2020). Virtual Assistance in Any Context. Business & Information Systems Engineering, 62(3), 211-225.
- Jones, VK (2018). "Voice-activated change: Marketing in the age of artificial intelligence and virtual assistants." ("Voice-Activated Change: Marketing in the Age of Artificial Intelligence ...") ("Artificial intelligence in marketing: A systematic literature review") Journal of Brand Strategy, 7(3), 233-245.

- Kim, J., & McMillan, SJ (2008). Evaluation of internet advertising research: A bibliometric analysis of citations from key sources. *Journal of Advertising*, 37(1), 99-112. (“Sally J. McMillan - Google Scholar”) (“Sally J. McMillan - Google Scholar”)
- Kraus, S., Roig-Tierno, N., & Bouncken, RB (2019). "Digital innovation and venturing: an introduction into the digitalization of entrepreneurship." (“Sci-Hub | Digital innovation and venturing: an introduction into the ...”) (“Sci-Hub | Digital innovation and venturing: an introduction into the ...”)
- Lehrer, C., Wieneke, A., Vom Brocke, JAN, Jung, R., & Seidel, S. (2018). How big data analytics enables service innovation: materiality, affordance, and the individualization of service. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 35(2), 424-460. (“How Big Data Analytics Enables Service Innovation: Materiality ...”) (“How Big Data Analytics Enables Service Innovation: Materiality ...”)
- Liu, B., Xu, Z., Sun, C., Wang, B., Wang, X., Wong, DF, & Zhang, M. (2017). Content-oriented user modeling for personalized response ranking in chatbots. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 26(1), 122-133. (“出版文献 | Min Zhang(张民)”) (“出版文献 | Min Zhang(张民)”)
- Mirsch, T., Lehrer, C., & Jung, R. (2017). Digital nudging: Altering user behavior in digital environments. *Proceedings der thirteen. Internationalen Tagung Wirtschaftsinformatik (WI 2017)*, 634-648.
- Mittal, P., & Singh, Y. (2016). Development of intelligent transportation system for improving average moving and waiting time with artificial intelligence. (“Role of Virtual Assistance In Digital Marketing”) (“Role of Virtual Assistance in Digital Marketing”) *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 9(3), 1-7.

Nangoy, JG, & Shabrina , NH (2020, November). "Analysis of Chatbot-Based Image Classification on Social Commerce LINE@ Platform." ("Analysis of Chatbot-Based Image Classification on Social Commerce LINE ...") ("Art painting identification using convolutional neural network") "In 2020 7th NAFOSTED Conference on Information and Computer Science (NICS) (pp. 232-237)." ("Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...") ("Transition from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing: A ...") IEEE.

Nguyen, QN, & Sidorova, A. (2018). "Understanding user interactions with a chatbot: A self-determination theory approach." ("AMCIS 2018 Proceedings - Association for Information Systems") ("AMCIS 2018 Proceedings - Association for Information Systems")

Oinas-Kukkonen , H., & Harjuma , M. (2009). Persuasive systems design:

Key issues, process model, and system features. ("Persuasive systems design: Key issues, process model, and system ...") ("Persuasive systems design: Key issues, process model, and system ...") "Communications of the Association for Information Systems, 24(1), 28." ("Designing User Interfaces for a Wellbeing Persuasive App") ("Application of Persuasive Techniques in the design of mobile eHealth ...")

Okumus , A., Bozbay , Z., and Dagi , RM (2010). Bank Customers to Internet Banking Related Attitudes Examination . Erciyes University Economic and Administrative Sciences Faculty Journal, (36), 89-111.22.

Ozmen , S. I. (2012). Virtual In the world of success Path Map and Electronic of marketing Dimensions . Journal of Internet Applications and Management,2(1), 37-47.23. Plaza, B. (2011). Google Analytics formeasuringwebsite performance.

- Tourism Management, 32(3), 477-48124.
- Pilato, G., Augello, A., Vassallo, G., & Gaglio, S. (2008). EHeBby : An evocative humorist chat-bot. *Mobile Information Systems*, 4(3), 165-181.
- Reddy, K. (2021). Changing Face of Shopping Behavior from Physical to Digital: A study in COVID 19 Pandemic. ("Changing Face of Shopping Behavior from Physical to Digital: A study in ...") ("Changing Face of Shopping Behavior from Physical to Digital: A study in ...") *Science, Technology and Development*, 10(V), 528-537.
- Richardson, M., & Domingos, P. (2002, July). Mining knowledge -sharing sites for viral marketing. In *Proceedings of the eighth ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and datamining* (pp. 61-70). ACM.25.
- Schneider, C., Weinmann, M., & Vom Brocke, J. (2018). Digital nudging: guiding online user choices through interface design. *Communications of the ACM*, 61(7), 67-73.
- SHAH, K. (2021). Covid-19's Impact on Digital Marketing Industry. Retrieved 22 October 2021, from <http://www.businessworld.in/article/Covid-19-s-Impact-On-Digital-Marketing-Industry/12-08-2021-400438/>
- Singh, J., & Sirdeshmukh, D. (two thousand). Agency and trust mechanisms in consumer satisfaction and loyalty judgments. *Journal of the Academy of marketing Science*, 28(1), 150-167.26.
- Srinivasan, S. S., Anderson, R., & Ponnavaolu, K. (2002). Customer loyalty in e-commerce: an exploration of its antecedents and consequences. *Journal of retailing*, 78(1), 41-50.27. Tan, A., Baydas, A., and Aksen, N. (2004). Kahramanmaras in your province of businesses Marketing in its activities internet Use trends . KSU. science

and Journal of Engineering , 7 (2), 83-89

Todor Raluca, D. (2016). Blending traditional and digital marketing. Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Bratov Series V: Economic Sciences, 9(58).

Todor, RD (2016). Blending traditional and digital marketing. Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov. Economic Sciences. Series V, 9(1), 51.

Todor, RD (2016). Blending traditional and digital marketing. Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov. Economic Sciences. Series V, 9(1), 51.

Vekleko , K. (2020). "Effectiveness of online advertising: a bibliometric analysis (Master's thesis, University of Twente)." ("Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A ...") ("Transition from Traditional Marketing to Digital Marketing: A ...")